

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

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*Elektron nashr. 356 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 7-noyabrda ruxsat etildi.*

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huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori
bilan ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

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REFORMS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKSITAN

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola O'zbekiston Respublikasidagi barcha davlat va nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining (OTM) faoliyatini tahlil qilishga qaratilgan. Tahlilning asosiy maqsadi bugungi kunda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarning mavjud muammolarni bartaraf etishda qanday samarali natija berayotganini aniqlashdir. Shu bilan birga, maqolada respublikadagi umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalari soni va ularda ta'lim olayotgan o'quvchilar soni ham ko'rsatilgan. Bu ko'rsatkichlar orqali OTMlarning ta'lim qamrov darajasini baholash va umumiy ta'lim tizimiga nechog'lik mos kelishini aniqlash maqsad qilib olingan.

Kalit so'zlar: aholi, maktab bitiruvchilar, maktablar, Oliy ta'lim muassasasi, islohot.

Abstract: This article aims to analyze the activities of all state and non-state higher education institutions (HEIs) in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main goal of the analysis is to determine how effective the current reforms are in addressing existing problems. At the same time, the article presents the total number of secondary educational institutions in the republic and the number of students enrolled in them. Through these indicators, the aim is to evaluate the level of educational coverage of HEIs and assess how well they integrate into the general education system.

Key words: population, school graduates, schools, higher education institution, reform.

Аннотация: Целью данной статьи является анализ деятельности всех государственных и негосударственных высших учебных заведений (ВУЗов) Республики Узбекистан. Основная цель анализа — определить, насколько эффективны текущие реформы в решении существующих проблем. В статье также указано общее количество средних общеобразовательных учреждений республики и количество студентов, обучающихся в них. Целью этих показателей является оценка уровня образовательного охвата вузов и определение, насколько хорошо они интегрируются в систему общего образования.

Ключевые слова: население, выпускники школ, школы, высшее учебное заведение, реформа.

INTRODUCTION

Higher education plays a pivotal role in the socio-economic development of any country, serving as a cornerstone for cultivating a skilled workforce, fostering innovation, and advancing research. In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has embarked on an ambitious journey to reform its higher education system, aligning it with global standards and addressing the needs of a rapidly evolving knowledge-based economy. These reforms reflect the government's commitment to enhancing the quality, accessibility, and relevance of education in the context of both national and international challenges.

The transformation of Uzbekistan's higher education institutions (HEIs) has been driven by key strategic objectives, including the modernization of curricula, the integration of advanced pedagogical methods, the promotion of academic mobility, and the strengthening of partnerships with leading global universities. Additionally, significant efforts have been made to improve governance structures within HEIs, promote transparency, and ensure that educational outcomes align with labor market demands. These initiatives are encapsulated in various presidential decrees and development programs, which emphasize innovation, digitalization, and the creation of a competitive academic environment.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Foreign researchers Richard Murnane and Richard Nelson, in their article *“Improving the Performance of the Education Sector: The Valuable, Challenging, and Limited Role of Random Assignment Evaluations”*[3], explored the education system and its management. They mainly discussed their perspectives on the quality of education and its positive consequences.

Giancarlo Corsi, in his article *“Education Reform as a Global Phenomenon”*[4], highlighted both the negative and positive consequences of reforms in the field of education. Joseph Zajda shared his views on the impact of globalization on education in his research entitled *“Discourses of Globalization and Higher Education Reforms”*[5].

In the article *“Role of Universities in the Development of Civil Society and Social Transformation”*[6], Radhe Shyam Sharma asserts that HEIs play a crucial role as leaders in teaching, learning, research, and technology. He emphasizes that universities, through their pedagogical activities, provide professional training for high-level positions, while also bearing the responsibility of offering education essential for individual development. HEIs contribute new knowledge and skills needed to address the challenges of sustainable development in society, raise public awareness, and create the foundation for informed decision-making, responsible behavior, and consumer choice.

METHODOLOGY OF THE RESEARCH

The information presented in this article is based on the analysis of secondary data collected from various government ministries, agencies, and statistical reports. This analysis was further supplemented by workshops, focus group discussions, and expert surveys conducted with employers.

ANALYSIS AND RESULT

Currently, education reforms are seen as key indicators of economic and social progress. As a result, the initial reforms of New Uzbekistan have focused on the social sector, particularly education. Notable examples include the construction of approximately 70 new schools, an increase in preschool enrollment from 27% to 70%, and a rise in higher education enrollment from 9% to 38%. As President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev aptly stated, *“Increasing the quality of education is the only correct way for the development of New Uzbekistan”* [1]. The designation of 2023 as the *“Year of Attention to People and Quality Education”* aligns closely with this vision.

Furthermore, the implementation of major strategic initiatives underscores this commitment. These include the 2019 *“Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030,”* the 2022 *“New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026,”* the inclusion of education reforms in the revised 2023 Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the *“Uzbekistan-2030”* strategy.

Economic returns further highlight the importance of investing in education. For instance, while the state of Uzbekistan spends an average of 18,909 USD per child, the return on this investment is 77,291 USD—roughly four times the initial investment. By comparison, Japan allocates 182,103 USD per child, yielding a return of 2,176,818 USD, about 12 times the investment (Figure 1). These figures underscore the transformative potential of education as a long-term driver of development.

Figure 1. Investments per student for the full cycle of education and income in the form of value added (thousands of US dollars).

Source: Based on data from Buyuk Kelajak

The data reveals that an average of 231,263 USD is spent per citizen in Uzbekistan, with an estimated return of 3.1 million USD—approximately 13 times the initial investment. In Malaysia, the expenditure per citizen is 44,200 USD, yielding a return of 647,300 USD, or 15 times the investment. Meanwhile, in South Korea, an investment of 130,800 USD in a child’s education generates a return 17 times greater, amounting to 2.1 million USD.

Further analysis highlights discrepancies in educational investment per student. In 2015, Uzbekistan allocated 1,045 USD per student, compared to 1,140 USD in Turkey and 4,074 USD in Malaysia. This means that per-student expenditure in Uzbekistan was 140 USD lower than in Turkey and nearly four times less than in Malaysia (Figure 2). These comparisons emphasize the need for greater investment in education to bridge the gap and maximize returns.

Figure 2. Expenditure per pupil by country (as of 2015).

In Japan, this cost is 10,000 US dollars, which is 10 times more than that of a student from Uzbekistan. The next indicator of the analysis is the USA, in which an average of 12,300 US dollars was spent for one American student, which is 12 times more than for an Uzbek student.

Our next analysis indicator is focused on the number of students in the classroom, in which we can see the following data (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Average number of students in school classrooms.

In this table, we can see that while the average number of students in schools in Uzbekistan is 39, this figure is 34 in Turkey, 32 in Japan, and 27 in the USA. In the countries that are members of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), there are almost 21 students in classrooms.

The population of Uzbekistan is one of the fastest growing countries. The purpose of our analysis of the demographic indicator of our country is to determine the proportion of the population, especially among young people. Now, the demographic indicator of Uzbekistan in 2016 is 31.5 million. made up 32.1 million people in the next year. reached 545,000 people or increased by 1.6% (Figure 4).

Let us analyze the number of students enrolled in general secondary schools during the specified period. In 2022, 6,461,000 students were studying in 10,522 schools, which averages 615 students per school. By 2021, the number of students had increased by 3%. During this time, 233 new schools were constructed across the republic, reflecting a significant investment in expanding educational infrastructure (Figure 7).

Figure 7. The number of students in general secondary schools of the Republic of Uzbekistan is 1,000.

If we look at the average annual increase in the number of students, from 2016 to 2022, the number of students increased by 235 thousand per year. If we analyze the number of schools, we can see that the number of schools has increased by an average of 115 per year. From 2016 to 2022, we can see a 7.63% increase in the number of newly built schools. If we analyze the school by students, we can see that it has increased by 25 percent from 2016 to 2022.

If we analyze the number of school graduates in the key picture of our research work, 475 thousand students graduated in 2016, and 9.8 percent of graduates graduated in 2016. In the 2016 academic year, 466,000 (8.85 percent) graduates graduated from a total of 5,263,000 students. In 2018, 475,000 students graduated, which is 2% more than in 2017 (Figure 8).

Figure 8. The number of school graduates is one thousand.

In the 2019 academic year, a total of 280,000 graduates completed their studies in Uzbekistan's general schools, reflecting a 41% decrease compared to 2018. This number represents 4.54% of the total school population for that year. In 2020, however, the number of graduates increased by 174,000, or 38%. From 2020 to 2022, there was a further decline: in 2021, the number of graduates decreased by 12,000 compared to 2020, and in 2022, the decline continued, with a further decrease of 54,000 graduates.

To analyze the number of general school graduates applying to higher education institutions (HEIs), we first need to consider the number of HEIs operating in Uzbekistan. As of 2016, there were 70 higher education institutions in the country. The following year, this number increased to 72 with the opening of two new institutions (Figure 9).

Figure 9. The number of HEIs in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In 2018, it reached 98 due to the opening of new and HEIs branches, an increase of 26 compared to 2017. The number of HEIs became 119 in 2019, due to the opening of 21 new science centers. Due to the pandemic, the number of new HEIs reached 127 in 2020, in other words, we can see the opening of 9 new HEIs. For the next new academic year 2021-2022, 154 HEIs have started their activities, which is an increase of 27 compared to 2018.

The number of HEIs continued to grow, reaching 191 in 2022, and the highest number of HEIs opened this year. In the next 2023-2024 academic year, 212 HEIs will start operating in Uzbekistan. Now, the main purpose of providing statistical information about the students of the above school is shown as an analysis, as it is directly related to HEIs. Currently (October 2023), according to the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan [6], a total of 212 HEIs can be divided into 3 types:

1. State - 116;
2. Non-state - 66;
3. Foreign - 30.

In the next table, if we look at those who submitted applications to higher education institutions, in 2016, 673 thousand applicants submitted applications, while the number of higher education institutions was 70. So, on average, according to the books, 9,615 applicants corresponded to 1 HEIs. In 2017, we can see that the number of applicants increased by 113 thousand (14 percent), while the number of school graduates was 466 thousand in this year, there were 40 percent more applicants than graduates (Figure 10).

Figure 10. The number of applicants to HEI (thousands).

In 2018, the number of applicants for higher education institutions (HEIs) reached 813,000, marking a 4% increase compared to 2017. The number of graduates that year was 475,000. With 98 HEIs in the country, the average number of students per institution was 8,295. In 2019, the number of applicants rose to 1,157,000, an increase of 344,000 compared to 2018. By 2020, this figure surged to 1,820,000, representing an increase of 663,000 applicants over 2019. Notably, this growth is equivalent to the total number of applicants recorded in 2016. However, in 2021, there was a significant decline in the number of applicants, dropping by 34% to just under 500,000. Despite this, the number of HEIs in the republic had grown to 191, while the number of school graduates was recorded at 442,000. By 2022, the number of applicants rebounded to 1,656,000, showing an increase of nearly 400,000 or 27% compared to 2021. This dynamic trend reflects the fluctuating demand for higher education over recent years.

If we analyze the number of students admitted to HEIs, we will have the following information. So, in 2016, 475,000 students graduated from school, 673,000 applied to 70 higher education institutions, and 61,200

received student status. This means that 9 percent managed to become a student, and the remaining 91 percent, i.e. 610,000, could not enroll.

In 2017, with 466,000 school graduates, 320 of those who could not enter HEIs in previous years, a total of 786,000 applicants applied to become students at 72 HEIs, but only 63,000 people managed to become students. Interestingly, compared to 2016, when the admission parameter increased by 2.9%, the share of 15-19-year-olds in the demographic index of Uzbekistan this year is 2 million. It was 658 thousand, and our total population is 32 million. at the time of the establishment of the person (Fig. 11).

Figure 11. The number of students admitted to HEIs (thousands).

In 2018, the population of 15-19-year-olds will be 2.5 million. of which the number of school graduates was 476,000, a total of 813,000 applicants applied for admission to 98 universities, only 114,000 were students, 14% of those who applied became students. means If we compare with the previous year, we can see that it has increased by 44%.

In 2019, the population of 15-19 years old is almost 2.5 million. of which the number of school graduates was 480,000, a total of 1,157,000 applicants applied for admission to 119 universities, only 138,000 were students, 11% of those who applied were students. Idi means. If we compare with the previous year, we can see that it has increased by 17%.

In 2020, the population aged 15-19 will be almost 2.5 million. of which 6.2 million are studying in 10,181 schools. A total of 1.8 mln. 9.6% of applicants or 175,000 were students. This figure is 21% more than in 2019.

The demographic indicator of Uzbekistan will be 34.5 million in 2021. made up 2.5 million people aged 15-19. in this year, the number of all school institutions is 1.2 million with 442,000 graduates from 10,289. abuturient submitted documents for admission to 154 universities, only 236,000 or 19% became students.

In 2022, the number of school graduates was 388,000, a total of 1,656,000 applicants applied for admission to 191 higher education institutions, only 282,000 were students, which means that 17% of those who applied became students. If we compare with the previous year, we can see an increase of almost 16%.

Currently, in 2023, 212 HEIs are operating in our republic, and a total of 1,203,125 students are studying in these HEIs. If we consider by gender, the number of male students is—601,325, and the number of female students is 601,800 (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Composition of students studying at the Higher Education Institution by gender

1,203,000 of these students study at 212 HEIs in the following educational forms:

- Daytime;
- External;
- Evening;
- Joint;
- Remote.

If we analyze according to the form of education, we will have the following information, that is, 657 thousand students in the form of full-time education, 482 thousand in the form of part-time education, and about the same in the form of evening education 44,000 students bring education (Fig. 13).

Figure 13. The number of students studying in higher educational institutions.

According to the statistics of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2023, 657 thousand (54 percent) of 1,203 thousand students are studying in the form of full-time education, and 482 are studying part-time. thousand (40 percent) students, 43 thousand (3.65 percent), joint 11 thousand (0.9 percent) and distance education 8 thousand (0.6 percent) are studying.

If we analyze the number of graduates of higher education institutions, we can get the following information. In 2016 of our analysis, when 70 HEIs were operating in the republic, 61.2 thousand students were admitted and 67.2 thousand students graduated. Now, the number of those who entered is 6 thousand more than those who graduated, because those admitted in 2016 will graduate in 2020 according to the plan, and the student graduating in 2016 entered HEIs in 2012. In 2017, 66,300 students graduated from 63 HEIs across the country, and 786,000 candidates applied this year. In 2018, the number of higher education institutions operating was 98, and the number of their graduates was 64,100 (Figure 14).

Figure 14. The number of students who graduated from HEI (thousands).

In this analysis, a comparative study is conducted, examining data from the current year and comparing it with figures from four years prior. In 2019, the number of higher education institutions operating in Uzbekistan was 119. However, the number of graduates in 2019 corresponds to those who had submitted documents to higher education institutions in 2016. Specifically, in 2016, 673,000 applicants applied to universities, of whom 61,200 were admitted as students. Additionally, 67,400 students, or 9% more than those who entered, graduated. This discrepancy can be attributed to some students taking academic leave and graduating in subsequent years.

In 2020, the number of graduates increased to 70,800. These graduates were applicants who had submitted documents in 2017, when 786,000 individuals applied, and 63,000 were admitted as students. Moving forward

to 2021, the number of applicants in 2018 rose to 813,000, with 114,500 being admitted as students, of whom 84,000 graduated. In 2022, 104,000 students graduated, and these graduates were applicants who had applied to 119 higher education institutions in 2019. Out of 1,157,000 applicants, 138,100 were admitted as students.

To assess the coverage of higher education institutions (HEIs) in the Republic, we can analyze the following data: in 2016, 475,000 graduates emerged from 9,719 general schools, and the coverage level of the 70 higher education institutions at that time was 9% (Figure 15).

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The ongoing reforms in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan are laying the foundation for the introduction of a new management framework. This new system requires innovative approaches, which are essential for the development of an independent and evolving state. Higher education institutions must identify priorities and allocate resources accordingly to fulfill their objectives. Universities cannot be effective or sustainable unless they define clear strategies, set priorities, establish and implement teaching and research goals, and adapt their structures and operations to a changing environment.

These reforms mark a significant milestone in Uzbekistan's pursuit of a knowledge-based economy and global competitiveness. By focusing on modernization, innovation, and alignment with international standards, the reforms aim to transform higher education institutions into centers of excellence that will contribute to the country's socio-economic development.

Despite notable progress, challenges such as limited resources, infrastructure gaps, and the need for continued capacity-building persist. Addressing these challenges requires a sustained commitment to policy innovation, effective implementation, and collaboration between national and international stakeholders.

The reforms emphasize the importance of academic freedom, lifelong learning, and equitable access to quality education. If successfully maintained, these transformative measures will not only improve the global standing of Uzbekistan's higher education institutions but also equip future generations with the knowledge and skills necessary to succeed in an increasingly interconnected world. This comprehensive approach serves as a model for other nations undergoing similar educational transitions, underscoring the critical role of higher education in shaping the future of society.

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Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokr ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2024. № 11

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

